

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

A GREAT TURKISH SCHOLAR ABU NASR AL-FARABI AT TURK

Mammadova A.

Assoc. Prof. Dr.

Baku State University, Faculty of Oriental Studies

ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9055-2313

ABSTRACT

Abu Nasr Muhammad ibn Muhammad ibn Tarkhan ibn Uzlug ibn Tarkhan (873-950) known as Al-Farabius in Latin, is regarded as the father of Islamic philosophy in the Eastern world.

The renowned Turkish scientist with encyclopedic knowledge established the Islamic world's Peripatetic philosophy (Aristotelianism) and was known as "The Second Teacher" (Al-mu'allim al-Sani) after the ancient Greek philosopher Aristotle. Abu Nasr Al-Farabi was born into a military family in Farab's Vesich village (now Otrar city), near the confluence of the Aris and Syr-Darya rivers. The scientist, who acquired his early education in Bukhara and Samarkand, traveled to Baghdad, Egypt, and Damascus in 910-911 to study with the renowned scientists of the East.

He had a significant impact on the development of classical scientific-philosophical teachings in both Eastern and Western philosophy. Although it is estimated that the great thinker's legacy in many disciplines of research is approximately 200 treatises, 117 interesting volumes have come down to us. Fourth-three of these works are about logic, 11 about metaphysics, 7 about political science, 7 about ethics, and 17 about music, medicine, and sociology. In the history of thought, Al-Farabi's fundamental commentaries on Aristotle's 11 writings revealed the philosopher's main concepts.

Al-Farabi was also a scientist who contributed significantly to the study of world music culture. The author not only commented on the theories of Greek scientists in his works on musicology, "The Book on the Classification of Rhythms," "A Word on Music," and "The Big Book on Music," but also proved his attitude to many of their false statements with strong evidence and facts, as well as extensive scientific analyses. With their scientific worth, studies that include subtle details such as the unmistakable power of exquisite music on the human spirit and the fact that this field of influence takes varied colors depending on the hours of the day are of tremendous relevance in our modern times. "The book on the art of public speaking," "The book on the art of letters," "The book on calligraphy," "The book on letters and pronunciation," and so on, which represent one of the key directions of the thinker philosopher's multifarious creativity, his linguistic studies are also notable for their unique place in the history of philological thought.

Keywords: al-Farabi, philosophy, Eastern culture, philosopher, music.

INTRODUCTION

The renowned Turkish scientist with encyclopedic knowledge established the Islamic world's Peripatetic philosophy (Aristotelianism) and was known as "The Second Teacher" (Al-mu'allim al-Sani) after the ancient Greek philosopher Aristotle. Abu Nasr Al-Farabi was born into a military family in Farab's Vesich village (now Otrar city), near the confluence of the Aris and Syr-Darya rivers. The scientist, who acquired his early education in Bukhara and Samarkand, traveled to Baghdad, Egypt, and Damascus in 910-911 to study with the renowned scientists of the East.

"The book on the art of public speaking," "The book on the art of letters," "The book on calligraphy," "The book on letters and pronunciation," and so on, which represent one of the key directions of the thinker philosopher's multifarious creativity, his linguistic studies are also notable for their unique place in the history of philological thought.

Al-Farabi has had researchers at various levels all throughout the world over the ages, in an Eastern-Western framework. In Azerbaijan, scholars of this encyclopedic genius include A. Mustafa, D. Huseynova, S. Farajov, Z. Mammadov, M. Kheyrollayev, and others. Researchers from all around the world have investigated

this outstanding Turkish scientist's large-scale, one-of-a-kind inventiveness from various perspectives.

Al-Farabi was a poet, physician, philosopher, and musician. All East Asian intellectuals, beginning with Ibn Sina, referred to him as their teacher. After Aristotle, Western scientists regarded him as the second greatest teacher. Many stories have been told about this brilliant scholar who resided in Baghdad, Aleppo, and Damascus. "One day, the Sultan of Aleppo, Seif al-Dawlat, invites scholars and poets to the palace," one of them says. Farabi enters the palace while on a visit, but does not welcome the assembly members. The congregation goes silent. The ruler invites him to have a seat. He inquires of the ruler as to where he should seat. The Sultan responds, "No one is shown a place. That's why each guest took the seat he thought he earned".

The Sultan was approached by Abu Nasir Muhammad al-Farabi, who requested him to step aside. The scientist's proposition surprises the ruler's attendants. Without hesitation, the Sultan seats the visitor next to him. He turns to the assembly members and says, "If the visiting guest is truly a wise man, we will forgive him for this action." Otherwise, he will be punished. Then, in a language that others could not understand, he instructs people around him, "You need to be patient and wait!" "You are absolutely correct," Al-Farabi said

to the ruler. Patience is a quality shared by the wise and powerful."

The ruler inquires of the wise scholar as to how he comprehended his statements. Farabi claims that nothing here is shocking. Because he is fluent in seventy languages. "The first word is yours," the perplexed ruler says after regaining consciousness. We are prepared to pay close attention to you!"

The old scholar first introduces himself to the meeting attendees. He then claims to have been born in the year 256-257 Hijri, or 870 according to the revised date, into the family of a Turkic-Kipchak soldier named Otrar. The Arabic word Otrar signifies "beautiful" and literally means "farab." His surname is derived from this word as well... [11]

Farabi was also a brilliant mathematician and astronomer. He studied Euclid's geometry and contributed to Ptolemy's astronomical encyclopedia. For almost a thousand years, his treatises have been taught in world science centers.

FUNDAMENTAL INVESTIGATION

The approach of the renowned philosopher to secular faiths

The scientist's view on religions is likewise highly unique and philosophical in nature. According to Al-Farabi, all religions aim for the center.

This focal point is God himself. From this vantage point, Al-Farabi possesses a certain tolerance that is characteristic of our modern period. For example, he claims that what divides individuals is not their religious differences, but their lack of awareness of the truth. This fact is that, despite their various degrees of existence and phases of spiritual advancement, all humans are created by the Divine Will.

Abu Mansur al-Farabi, who delves deeply into the question of truth's unity, devotes significant room to a detailed and passionate portrayal of the prophet's personality. According to him, the prophet is a holy man who achieves the pinnacle of philosophy as well as spiritually. (8, international) As can be seen, the genius philosopher's beliefs about tolerance shed light on our current society centuries ago.

HIS VIEWS ON THE STATE, STATEHOOD, AND HAPPINESS

The scientist wrote treatises on social and moral concerns, including "Book on the Views of the Virtuous City People," "Book on Achieving Happiness," "Showing the Way to Happiness," "Citizen Policy," "On Virtuous Morality," and "Study of Society." He referred to ancient Eastern social ideas, Greek philosophers' teachings, particularly Plato and Aristotle, and proposed a theory of social structure based on strict moral, legal, and political laws" [4, 49].

As a result, because the ideal state was founded in accordance with divine precepts, its residents should be fully content. The state's responsibility was to ensure the happiness of its inhabitants. Al-Farabi goes into great length regarding the essence of happiness and how to obtain it. Happiness, according to al-Farabi, has three essential conditions:

1. Happiness is a purely theoretical activity;
2. Happiness is a purely practical activity;
3. Happiness is a combination of the two.

Despite the fact that the genuine techniques of gaining happiness are revealed to be the outcome of individual, personal effort, happiness can be reached thanks to the unity of people, more specifically, in the framework of society, by accepting God, according to the moral principles of Farabi's described bliss. Farabi appears to link the necessity of perfect state-building to the existence of a supreme ideal judge [10, int. res.].

In his book "Ways to Happiness," Abu Mansur al-Farabi argues, "philosophy came to us from the Greeks, Plato and Aristotle." Each of them taught us not only philosophy, but also how to get there and how to recreate it when it is lost or falling into decay.

Ibn Sina, Bahmanyar, Nizami, Ibn Rushd, Safiedin Urmavi, N. Tusi, and Ibn Khaldun all benefited from Al-Farabi's scientific and philosophical legacy.

Al-Farabi made incomparable contributions to mathematics, philosophy, medicine, biology, linguistics, and music, and he became famous for his commentary on Aristotle's works.

Al-Farabi was one of the earliest intellectuals to convey Greek philosophy to the Islamic, Eastern worlds. He is also considered one of the first researchers in physics to comment on the existence of voids and theirs.

A SHOLAR'S TREATISE ON MUSIK

Each nation is different with its history, culture and shows its influence on other nations. Music is an integral part of the history and culture of any nation, and the basis of this genre is the chord-intonation structure. Lad is created on the basis of aspects specific to the nation's national and moral values, and thus that music contains most of the characteristics of the nation [1, 23].

One of Al-Farabi's biggest achievements was his love of music and scientific study. Al-Farabi split music science into theoretical and practical components in his famous work "Kitab al-musiqā al-kabir" - "The Great Book of Music," and computed the internal arrangement and regularities of the song. He used facts to interpret the rhythmic underpinning of Eastern music. Al-Farabi was a well-known composer and developer of new musical instruments. He gave serious impetus to the development of musicology with his dissertation "The Great Book of Music." Al-Farabi created the sound system employed in modern Arabic music. [8, intern. res.]

Al-Farabi's intimate understanding of music, as well as his ability to play many musical instruments, prompted him to compose such a faultless work as "Kitab al-musiqā al-kabir." In terms of learning and researching ancient Turkish and Eastern national music, this book is an exceptionally significant resource for research musicologists.

Even now, for research musicologists, the work "Kitab al-musiqā al-kabir" - "The Great Book of Music" - is a very significant source for studying and investigating old Turkish and Eastern national music. "A Word on Music" and "Book on the Classification of Rhythms" are also accessible. In these works, the author not only commented on Greek scientists' beliefs, but also demonstrated his stance on many of their incorrect statements with strong proof and facts, as well as detailed scientific research. "Studies that include subtle nuances, such as the undeniable influence of wonderful music on the human soul and the fact that

this sphere of influence takes different shades according to the hours of the day, are of great relevance in our modern times with their scientific value" [2, 163].

There was once a belief that music and poetry were a tax, bestowed exclusively on the favorites by revelation. However, the notion that this gift may be nurtured and increased by working on oneself professionally emerged later. Based on the laws of music and rhythm, genius scientist Khalil ibn Ahmad Farahidi devised aruz, which is the major weight of pearls of world literature from the 7th century to the present. Because of successive historical triumphs in this field in the Eastern world, the first work on music theory in the Islamic world was produced around the end of the 8th century and muslim musicians and philosophers began deep scientific investigation and methodical action in the subject of music in the 9th century.

Thus, from this century to the end of the 13th century, al-Kindi, Ikhwanus-safa, Ibn Sina, and al-Farabi created the groundwork for intellectual advancement with a vibrant musical culture defined by distinctive genres and instruments. When it comes to national music, Uzeyir Hajibeyli observes that the Middle Eastern musical culture peaked in the 14th century. He compares this civilization to a high palace with a panoramic perspective of the world, from Andalusia to China, from Central Africa to the Caucasus. At the same time, he mentions that prominent thinkers like Abu Nasr al-Farabi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, and al-Kindi helped build that opulent palace of musical culture [3, 82-83]. Music history, theory, philosophy, and all other related areas were combined in the science known as "ilm al-musica" in medieval Muslim culture.

Because they considered music theory to be tied to philosophy, medieval music researchers were also interested in old philosophical texts, therefore they translated treatises on ancient Greek and Hellenistic science and philosophy. Translations into Arabic grew more common in this field during the 8th and 11th centuries. The tradition of authoring intellectual treatises on music persisted until the end of the 17th century, when the influence of European music became increasingly widespread [3, 19].

Farabi observes that instrumental music evolved from vocal music and that the more it mimics the human voice, flawless it is. In this regard, he believes rubab, mizmar, oud, and mizaf to be the ideal musical instruments. He finds the human voice to be flawless, distinguishing it not only by its tone, but also by the consistency of its sounding. If the instrument being played is not accompanied by vocal music, that instrument takes on the function of the principal voice, echoing the main melodic line. The main musical instrument should be chosen in this scenario because it more closely mimics the human voice than the other musical instruments that accompany it. Al-Farabi also believes that the literary content of the melody in vocal music should have meaning, as music is merely a means to improve it [3, 122].

It is difficult to distinguish the effect of Islam and the Arab world on European music while examining Eastern and Western music. However, it can be said that, while Semitic thought and practice were felt early

on, Persian and Byzantine influences were more obvious later on, specifically during the period of Islam and the Arab Caliphate.

Conclusion and Evaluations:

- Abu Nasr Muhammad ibn Muhammad ibn Tarkhan ibn Uzlug ibn Tarkhan (873-950), known in Latin as Al-Farabius.

- Abu Nasr Al-Farabi al-Turk is considered the founder of Islamic philosophy in the Eastern world.

- A great Turkish scientist with encyclopedic intelligence laid the foundation of peripatetic philosophy (Aristotelianism) in the Islamic world.

- Al-Farabi was known as "The Second Teacher" (Al-mu'allim al-Sani) after the ancient Greek philosopher Aristotle.

- Although he is reported to have written around 200 treatises and scholarly works, only 117 of these have survived to the present day.

- All religions, according to al-Farabi, aim for the center. • The center is God himself.

- He proposed a philosophy of social organization based on stringent moral, legal, and political laws in his works.

- He split music science into theoretical and practical components, and calculated the internal arrangement and regularities of the tune.

- Al-Farabi's scientific and philosophical legacy provided a rich supply of information and ideas for Ibn Sina, Bahmanyar, Nizami, Ibn Rushd, Safiaddin Urmavi, Nasireddin Tusi, and Ibn Khaldun.

- Al-Farabi made incomparable contributions to mathematics, physics, philosophy, medicine, biology, linguistics, and music, and he is most known for his comments on Aristotle's works.

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